

RESEARCH OF IQ-SPECTRA DURING PROCESSING OF SECONDARY POLYETHYLENE

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Abstract. The article presents the results of a study of the IQ spectra of recycled polyethylene waste. To plasticize recycled polyethylene waste, a mixture of soap stock and dioctyl phthalate in a 1:1 ratio was used as a plasticizer.

Keywords: secondary polyethylene, IQ spectrum, soapstock, asymmetric, symmetrical, infrared spectrum, dioctyl phthalate.

INTRODUCTION

In the research conducted on the study of the IQ-spectra of secondary polyethylene (PE) waste, in order to plasticize secondary polyethylene waste, a 1:1 mixture of waste soapstock and dioctyl phthalate was used as a plasticizer.

Experiment 1. Now for comparison, the infrared spectrum of the secondary PE sample in Figure 1 below was obtained:

Figure 1. IQ spectrum of secondary PE.

Table 1

Characteristic frequencies of secondary PE related to important groups in the IQ spectrum

The nature of vibration	Frequency, cm^{-1}	Intensity
PE $\nu_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{as}}$	2920,30	Strong
PE $\nu_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{s}}$	2846,93	Strong
$\delta_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{s}}$	1471,69	Average
PE $\gamma_{\text{C-C}}$	729,09	Weak

Experiment 2. Then the infrared spectrum of the soapstock sample in Figure 2 was obtained:

Figure 2. IQ spectrum of soapstock

Table 2

Characteristic frequencies of soapstock belonging to important groups in the IR spectrum

The nature of vibration	Frequency, cm ⁻¹	Intensity
ν_{OH} (connected)	3371,57	strong, average
$\nu_{CH_2}^{as}$	2922,16	Strong
$\nu_{CH_2}^s$	2852,72	strong, average
$\nu_{C=C}$	1645,28	average, weak
$\nu_{C=C}$ (double bond in an aromatic ring)	1548,84	average, weak
δ_{CH} (aromatic)	1463,97	average, weak
δ_{OH}	1406,11	Average
ν_{CO}^{as} (-C-O-H)	1085,99	average, weak
ν_{CO}^s (-C-O-H)	1053,13	average, weak
δ_{CH} (alkene)	993,34	Weak

In experiment 2, the IQ spectrum of soapstock was obtained. This Table 2 shows the asymmetric and symmetric valence characteristic of CH₂, CH (aromatic), CH (alkene), C=C, CO, C=C (double bond in aromatic ring), OH (bonded) groups and other groups in soapstock values of fluctuations are given.

Experiment 3. Infrared spectra of samples of soapstock with secondary PE in 1:0.1, 1:0.3 and 1:0.5 mass units were obtained in the following figures 3.4.7, 3.4.8, 3.4.9:

Figure 3. Secondary PE + soapstock (0.1 m.b.) IQ spectrum

Figure 4. Secondary PE + soapstock (0.3 m.b.) IQ spectrum

Figure 5. Secondary PE + soapstock (0.5 m.b.) IQ spectrum

Table 2

Characteristic frequencies of secondary PE+soapstock (0.1, 0.3 and 0.5 m.b.) belonging to important groups in the IQ spectra

The nature of vibration	Frequency, cm ⁻¹	Intensity
PE $\nu_{\text{CH}_2^{\text{as}}}$	2918,30	Strong
PE $\nu_{\text{CH}_2^{\text{s}}}$	2848,86	Strong
Soapstock $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$	1634,01	Weak
Soapstock $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ (double bond in an aromatic ring)	1551,2	Weak
PE $\delta_{\text{CH}_2^{\text{s}}}$	1444,68	Average
Soapstock δ_{OH}	1423,47	Average
Soapstock $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{H}}^{\text{as}}$ (-C-O-H) for the group	1103,28	Weak
Soapstock $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{H}}^{\text{s}}$ (-C-O-H) for the group	1053,13	Weak
Soapstock δ_{CH} (alkene)	923,90	Weak
PE $\gamma_{\text{C}-\text{C}}$	823,60	Weak
Soapstock $\delta_{=\text{CH}}$	698,23	Average, weak

In experiment 3, IR spectra of secondary PE + soapstock mixed in ratios of 0.1, 0.3 and 0.5 were obtained. When secondary PE is mixed with soapstock in ratios of 0.1, 0.3 and 0.5, the values of asymmetric and symmetric valence vibrations specific to the SN2 group in PE (nsn2as) range from 2920.30 cm⁻¹ to 2848.86 cm⁻¹ and symmetric vibrations (nsn2s) can be seen to be slightly shifted from 2846.93 cm⁻¹ to 2848.86 cm⁻¹. Also, valence vibration ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$) characteristic of a double bond C=C in soapstock range from 1645,28 sm⁻¹ to 1634,01 sm⁻¹ and valence vibration $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ of a double bond characteristic of an aromatic ring (double bond in an aromatic ring) range bathochromically from 1548,84 sm⁻¹ to 1551,2 sm⁻¹.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the valence vibrations (noH) characteristic of the OH group in soapstock were manifested by a bathochromic shift indicating the presence of a broad-shaped hydrogen bond of weak intensity at 3381.67 cm^{-1} , with a strong intensity in the region of 3371.57 cm^{-1} . These changes in the macromolecule can be seen to increase the interaction bonds (dipole-dipole, electrostatic and hydrogen bonding) between PE and soapstock molecules.

According to the above experimental results, it can be concluded that the main reason for the improvement of the physical and mechanical properties of polymer macromolecules during the processing of (1:0.3 m.b.) secondary polyethylene mixtures is that the polymer macromolecules are completely mixed with soapstock and DOF molecules, and dipole-dipole. The occurrence of electrostatic, hydrogen bond and physical effects can be seen from the changes in the peaks in the above spectra. Secondary polyethylene mixtures with soapstock and DOF 1:0.3 m.b. obtained is an optimal working recipe, which can be used for the production and use of various plasticized polymer composite products for technical purposes.

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